

ANALYSIS OF IDIOMS AND PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS FROM A PRAGMATIC ASPECT

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Abstract: In this article, the author presents the results of empirical research on the use of words and phrases used in active communication in a foreign language, especially in English, in a pragmatic situation and their difference in pragmatic meaning. It examines the scope of their direct influence on translation processes.

Keywords: pragmatics, translation, anthropological approach, syntactic idioms, metaphor, phraseological units.

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Abstract: Ushbu maqolada muallif chet tilida xususan ingliz tilida faol muloqotda ishlatilib kelinayotgan so'z va iboralarning pragmatik vaziyatda qo'llanilishi va ularning pragmatik ma'no jihatidan farqlanishiga oid imperik tadqiqot natijalarini keltirib o'tadi. Ularning tarjima jarayonlariga bevosita ta'sir doirasini o'rganadi.

Keywords: pragmatika, tarjima, antropologik yondashuv, sintaktik idiomalar, metafora, frazeologik birliklar.

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Abstract: В данной статье автор представляет результаты эмпирического исследования употребления слов и словосочетаний, используемых в активном общении на иностранном языке, особенно на английском языке, в прагматической ситуации и их различие в прагматическом значении

Keywords: прагматика, перевод, антропологический подход, синтаксические идиомы, метафора, фразеологизмы.

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Introduction In the works of local and foreign researchers, various aspects related to phraseology are considered. It is noteworthy that when studying phraseological units in the context of the category of intensity, the interests of modern scientists are most often limited to the allocation of phraseological intensifiers and intensifiers, as well as the study of Tex structural and semantic transformations of phraseological units that increase its expressiveness. Sometimes the problems of syntactic idioms are also in the field of view of the authors. As for the study of the functional- pragmatic aspect of phraseological units, it is worth highlighting the works of those researchers who are based on the principle of anthropocentrism. With the anthropological approach, the human factor becomes

the main circumstance that determines the development, functioning and nature of phraseological units, in connection with which phraseological units are studied, as a rule, from two points of view: from the position of modeling their evaluative semantics, which conveys a versatile assessment of a person, his external and internal qualities, as well as their role and purpose in human verbal activity. Thus, when determining the functional- pragmatic aspect of phraseological units, a person and his speech are taken as a starting point.

Considering phraseological units as a strategic tool that contributes to the implementation of a speech strategy of increased impact on communication participants and as a distinctive characteristic of an emotional linguistic personality, it should be recognized that in the light of such an approach, amplifying phraseological units will be of particular interest. vividly representing the category of intensity. Among them, in turn, comparative phraseological units are distinguished, which, according to their semantic content, can be conditionally divided into several groups.

Method These phraseological units, in our opinion, not only enhance the degree of manifestation of the feature, but also to a certain extent specify the feature itself, making it more prominent and tangible, however, in accordance with the perception of the addresser. This position is consistent with the position of many researchers. So, A.F. Artemova believes that PU actualizes not so much an action (in our case, a sign) as its high degree, and not so much a real action as an idea of this action [1]. In the understanding of A.V. Fedoruk, phraseological units move the meaning from the world of observation and indication to the world of imagination and experience. Possessing a pronounced pragmatic purpose, phraseological units rather appeal to the emotional sphere of the human psyche and through it to the awareness of what is happening through intentional experience. The formation of the meaning of amplifying phraseological units in its typical manifestation can be represented as a process of metaphorization that synthesizes in itself inferential knowledge about the denotation (following from knowledge about the properties of the denoted) and its value qualification (which is a value judgment immersed in the context of opinion about the properties of the denoted)[2].. Amplifying FE, according to the author, do not are adapted to the function of denoting objects from the "Real" world, therefore their denotation is diffuse. They do not depict the world, but point to it only in order to "attribute" a sign to the signified. As a result, these phraseological units have the function of predication. Their adaptability to the function of predication is also due to the presence of evaluative and emotive modality in their semantic structure, which "load" phraseological units pragmatically, which is expressed in their expressiveness [3]. When transferred to a different language environment, it is rather difficult to preserve information about

the emotional and evaluative perception of reality by the subject of speech, as well as the degree of expressiveness inherent in the original phraseological unit. However, in those cases where in the source language and in the target language we have a full or partial match, this is quite possible.

As for the high pragmatic potential of phraseological units, modern authors associate it, first of all, with their figurativeness and with the fact that "as a rule, connotation prevails in the semantic structure of phraseological units" [4]. At the same time, different opinions are expressed in the linguistic literature about the relationship between denotative and connotative senses in the meanings of phraseological units. So, V.M. Mokienko believes that "... in phraseologism, the nominative is dissolved in the expressive, subordinate to it. These two sides of a linguistic sign in a phraseological unit are syncretic, while vocabulary (especially non-expressive B) is differentiated, disconnected" [5]. According to our point of view, the question of which macrocomponent prevails in the semantics of phraseological units should be considered on a specific language material.

-Comparative phraseological units, which have national specifics and thus reflect the cultural and national mentality of native speakers, deserve special attention. Such phraseological units, as a rule, intensify the sign, specify it, while simultaneously evaluating and conveying its perception by the subject of speech, for example: *más feo que el sargento de Urtera no skin, no mugs, es más fresco que una lechuga impudent to the limit, como la tripa de Jorge is like rubber, como pedrada en ojo de boticario* - most appropriate (very appropriate)

These linguistic units belong to the area of intersection of the functional-semantic fields of the intensity of the attributive feature and the assessment, which determines the specifics of their pragmatic constant. It should be noted that during the transformation their national and cultural identity disappears, leading to the loss of certain K stylistic characteristics and reducing the degree of expressiveness of the feature.

Consideration of the features of the pragmatic component of phraseological units proves that they convey information about the emotional and evaluative perception of reality by the subject of speech. communicants are intended, i.e. for enhanced transmission of intentionality can convey various emotionally - colored speaker's communicative intentions. At the same time, the intensifying value of phraseological units, according to many researchers, is formed as a result of cognitive transformations in such structures as frames and prototypes.

Frames, in the understanding of the authors of the theory of conceptual modeling of the actual meaning of idioms (Baranova A.N., Dobrovolsky D.O.), are conceptual structures with declaratively and procedurally oriented knowledge[6]. It is noteworthy that this theory is based on the position that any phraseological

unit corresponds to its own abstract conceptual frame structure. The formation of the meaning of phraseological units is explained by scientists in the context of a whole complex of transformations in conceptual structures, and not by the transfer of characteristics from one denotation to another and not by the derivative of some values from others. Of particular interest in the framework of our work is the study of the semantics of phraseological units from the position of a prototype, since its meaning is most often seen through the semantics of a phraseological unit, despite the high degree of abstraction that is characteristic of most of those units that belong to the means of expressing the category of intensity of an attributive feature. Cf. *soto* (el) *un diablo* awful, damn, very, too much; *soto un madero* (hecho un madero) - like a log, like a dead man, blockhead, cudgel, dumb as a stump, *hecho un loco* beside himself (from rabies, despair, etc.).

Results Obviously, a metaphorical rethinking of the prototype plays a big role in the formation of such phraseological units, therefore, in the HX meaning, not only the sense of intensity is singled out, but also the prototype underlying this or that phraseological unit. At the same time, it should be noted that the prototypes of phraseological units are understood as “not only linguistic units or variable combinations of words, but also various kinds of associative relations, i.e. a fund of general knowledge related to historical traditions, facts, realities, religious beliefs and their attributes” [7].

According to E.Yu. Kunitsyna, is the presence of an irrational moment (the main parameter of the internal form), which is quite comparable with the transition from one level of cognition to another. The internal form, in turn, is such a significative content of the rethought linguistic unit, which is directly related to the epistemological image of the cognized and named object [8].

The basis of the internal form of phraseological units, according to many authors, is the derivational connection between the meaning of phraseological units and the meaning of the prototype, so that the internal form of amplifying phraseological units appears as an intermediary between the new meaning of intensity and correlation with reality through the subject-logical meaning of a free combination of words. As for the intensifying meaning of phraseological units, it is recognized as a consequence of the process of metaphorization, which is closely connected with the feeling of similarity / similarity of the emerging typical image of reality with some “concrete”, figuratively associative representation of another reality, its prototype. At the same time, the metaphor is designed to be aware of various aspects of some concepts in terms of others, as well as to identify and create similarities between two dissimilar phenomena based on their implicit / explicit comparison. With the assumption of similarity and similarity, the movement of thought begins, which, building them into an analogy, then already synthesizes a

new concept, which, on the basis of a metaphor, receives the form of an intensifying meaning (Kunin 1996; Teliya 1996; Fedoryuk 2001)

Discussion Thus, the recipient is faced with the task of comprehending one or another metaphorical unit, giving preference to one of those potential meanings that can be realized within the framework of the corresponding metaphorical predication. As follows from the results of the analysis of the factual material, a large role in this case plays a correct understanding of the communicative situation and context, which help to limit the number of possible meanings of phraseological units to a minimum. In terms of reflecting the subjective feelings and assessments of the speaker in a speech act containing phraseological units. it can be argued that it is achieved through the subjectivation of emotional phraseological evaluation and personal interpretation of specific reality through the prism of a phraseological image The high frequency of the use of amplifying phraseological units is observed in the novel by M. Delibes "Cinco horas con Mario". This circumstance, firstly, is explained by the form of the work, which is a monologue of the heroine, and secondly, confirms the fact that phraseological units are characteristic primarily for colloquial speech, where phraseological units can not only enhance the expressiveness of the statement, but also serve as an indicator of a pragmatic attitude addressee. It is no coincidence that when analyzing discursive distributions of Phraseological intensifiers in modern English (PUs like as the devil, like a shot, like crazy, like a house afire, like one o'clock, etc.), A.V. Fedoryuk comes to the conclusion that if in the system- linguistic description these units are most often presented as signs of secondary predication, then in discourse they behave as signs of illocution, i.e. indicate how exactly the proposition in the statement should be understood. In this property, according to the researcher, lies their symbolic specificity. According to our analysis, as well as the observations of other researchers, the optimization of speech strategies and the enhancement of the expressiveness of an attributive feature are most clearly manifested when using phraseological units containing an explicit (explicit) comparison. At the same time, a high degree of manifestation of a feature is realized both with the help of comparison and with hyperbolization of the feature. In the latter case, as a rule, there is an indication of the consequence, to which such a high intensification of a feature / quality leads, for example: 1. You are free as air, you are not bound by anything, know it, know it! - Eres libre como el aire: nada, nada te liga conmigo, sabelo bien (Turgenev); 2. Esperad, que tan buen pan hacen aqui como en Francia. Wait, and we bake bread no worse than in other places. (Galdos); 3. Los bultos, con los ojos ya más sosegados, iban marchando pero aun quedaban algunos aferrados al ataúd como las moscas al papel matamoscas. The ghosts with already calm eyes all left, but some of them stuck to the coffin like sticky flies.

In the first case, we see the full correspondence of phraseological units used in the source and in the translation. In the second, partial, and in the third, with the coincidence of individual components, we are dealing with phraseological units that are completely different in meaning, which led to a distortion of the author's pragmatic attitude.

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